

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY FOR THE PRODUCTION OF SWEET PRODUCTS BASED ON MELON FRUIT

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ABSTRACT

The object of research: the process of creating a technology for the preparation of sweet products using locally produced melon fruits.

Investigated goal: Development of technology for the production of sweet products from gourds on a natural basis using local unsold raw materials.

Main scientific results: possible ways of using unsold melon fruits in the food industry were identified, a solution to the problem of overproduction of melons and gourds in the country was proposed. The original technologies for the production of sweet products made on the basis of the fruits of gourds have been compiled and worked out. the evaluation of the nutritional value of finished products was carried out.

Area of practical use of research results: small and medium-sized farms for the production of melon fruits.

Innovative technological product: technology for the production of sweet products, which allows organizing the industrial processing of the unsold volume of gourds.

Scope of the innovative technological product: agricultural and food industry in the field of melons processing, small and medium enterprises for the production of melons, confectionery production.

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1. Introduction

1. 1. The object of research

The object of research is the process of creating a technology for the preparation of sweet products using locally produced melon fruits.

1. 2. Problem description

According to world statistics, the Republic of Kazakhstan is in the top 15 countries for the production of melons and gourds. Kazakhstan occupies the 6th place in terms of the volume of melons produced from the total world production, and the 11th place in terms of the volume of grown watermelons. Every year, the value of the gross harvest and productivity of melons and gourds increases in the country [1, 2].

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, melons and gourds during the growing season make up a significant share of the total diet of every citizen. The consumption of melon and watermelon fruits provides the body with a number of substances, especially carbohydrates, vitamins, micro- and macroelements.

However, gourds, especially melons and watermelons, have a low keeping quality, which in turn complicates the process of their preservation for a long period of time. Industrial processing of fruits into food products among gourds is established only from pumpkin, there are no technologies for the production of food products from watermelons and melons today. The crop processing industry does not have the proper technical equipment and offers for the industrial production of products based on melons and watermelons. Meanwhile, out of the total volume of melons and gourds grown, only a part enters the trade turnover to meet the domestic needs of the country's population and export

abroad. About 40 % of the grown crop volume annually remains in the field of cultivation and is not subject to further sale. There is a high overproduction of gourds in the country [3]

The world community of the 21st century is showing particular interest in environmental issues, one of which is the problem of providing the population with a healthy and balanced diet. The resolution of the situation is based on the creation of new food products made from non-traditional raw materials with high biological value.

Analysis of the base of peer-reviewed scientific literature Scopus on the availability of technologies for processing melons and gourds showed the absence of a constant interest of the scientific community in the issues of fruit processing – scientific papers are published with long breaks in time, there is a cyclical process from growing interest to a sharp decline in scientific activity in this direction.

According to data published in scientometric databases, there is a growing interest in studying the possibilities of processing melons and watermelons into long-term storage products with increased biological value. However, the vast majority of work is focused on processing methods for whole fruits in order to increase shelf life. At the moment, ways to use grafting and spraying fruits are being studied [4].

Part of the research is aimed at developing methods for extracting compounds from secondary raw materials from melon fruits. Thus, the technology was developed and the technology for extracting bioethanol from melon peel was optimized [5].

Among the works of foreign scientists on the study of the properties of the fruits of gourds, information on the creation of a technology for their processing and the creation of food products based on them was not found.

1. 3. Suggested solution to the problem

The described problem can be solved by developing a technology for the production of sweet products based on unsold melon fruits. A working hypothesis for the possibility of creating new products can be the assumption that melon fruits have a high nutritional value, the processing of fruits will significantly increase the shelf life of finished products. Indirect confirmation of this hypothesis is contained, for example, in the scientific studies of foreign scientists, such as

Cucumis melo L. – honey melon, a fruit of the gourd family. In appearance, a ripe melon is an oval fruit with a white-yellow rind, the flesh has a similar color, sweet taste and aroma. According to the chemical composition, it is rich in the presence of vitamins B₁ (thiamine), B₂ (riboflavin), B₉ (folic acid), C (ascorbic acid) and β-carotene [6]. The concentration of sugars, in particular sucrose, 5-methyltetrahydrofolate, provitamin A and soluble solids in different parts of the fetus can vary significantly. [7].

The chemical composition and properties give the melon a number of properties recognized as healing, and therefore the plant is considered a means of preventing and treating several groups of diseases in alternative medicine. For example, melon is recommended for use by patients with problems of the cardiovascular system, liver, kidneys, anemia, rheumatism, gout and atherosclerosis. Pleasant flavor and aroma properties of the fruit make it very attractive not only as a remedy for diseases, but also as a sweet fruit dessert [8].

The study of the possibility of producing products based on the fruits of gourds has been carried out for several years, ways of processing the pulp of melon and watermelon fruits into ready-to-eat food products are being studied [9].

Previously, a study was conducted on the production of melon gummy candies. [10] within the framework of this work, the recipe composition and marmalade production technology were modernized.

The aim of research was to develop technologies for processing the unrealizable volume of melon fruits into sweet products of increased nutritional value.

2. Materials and methods

2. 1. Method for obtaining melon puree

The fruits of the melon were cut, the seeds were removed, the pulp was separated from the peel. Clean pulp was crushed mechanically into pieces of 50x50 cm. chopped melon was crushed to a puree state using a blender.

2. 2. Technical analysis

The content of proteins, fats and carbohydrates in the finished product was determined according to the methods described in Using Watermelon Peel and Charlene Melon Husk as a Natural Source of Dietary Fiber and Antioxidants in Cake – ScienceDirect.

Determination of the organoleptic quality of melon jelly marmalade was carried out on the basis of the requirements of CXS 296-2009 “STANDARD FOR JAMS, JELLIES AND JELLIES” [11].

The development of the optimal production technology was carried out on the basis of the methodology of the full factorial experiment. Watermelons and melons were bought at the local market and at KazRIPVG. Variety of melons is predominantly “Valet”, cultivar watermelon – “Zhetygen”.

The production of Turkish delight was carried out according to traditional technology with the addition of specialized, recommended food additives [12].

3. Results

3. 1. Melon marmalade

Melon pulp was used as the main raw material in the production of marmalade sweets. Melon is a product with a high moisture content, as a result of which it is a favorable environment for the development of microorganisms. To provide an antiproferative effect, powder from dried rowan fruits was included in the marmalade formulation.

The chemical composition of the raw material, in our case, melon puree, is shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1

The chemical composition of melon puree

Nutrient	Quantity	Norm**	% of norm in 100 g	% of the norm in 100 kcal	100 % normal
Calories	337 kcal	1684 kcal	20 %	5.9 %	500 g
Proteins	0.04 g	76 g	0.1 %	–	190000 g
Fats	0.01 g	56 g	–	–	560000 g

3. 2. Turkish delight from melon

Melon puree was used as the basis for making Turkish delight. The duration of the total cooking time of the finished product is indicated per serving with the mass of the main ingredient – 400 grams.

The first stage in determining the quality of experimental samples is organoleptic analysis.

Based on the results of sensory analysis, average values were derived for each of the five indicators for four samples of Turkish Delight. A visual comparison of the results is shown in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1. Profilogram of organoleptic indicators of Turkish Delight based on melon puree

Based on the results of sensory analysis using the program Statistica 12.0, profilograms of the analysis of the optimum, the average values and the response surface were constructed. The results are shown in **Fig. 2–5**.

Fig. 2. Optimum analysis profilogram

Fig. 3. Established response surface according to the desirability function of organoleptic quality indicators of Turkish delight based on melon depending on the amount of starch and the duration of heat treatment

Fig. 4 shows the physico-chemical composition – Turkish delight from melon puree.

Fig. 4. Mass fraction of proteins, fats, carbohydrates in melon pulp and Turkish delight based on it

The mass fraction of carbohydrates in melon pulp is 6.58 %, in the finished product 17.48 %. The fat content in the raw material is 0.3 %, in the product sample – 0.34 %. The mass fraction of protein in the pulp is 0.63 %, in the finished Turkish delight – 0.98 %.

Fig. 5. Mass fraction of vitamin C in melon pulp and Turkish delight based on it

The content of vitamin C is 16.22 mg/100 g of vegetable raw materials, 100 grams of the finished product contains 16.2 mg of ascorbic acid.

4. Discussion

4. 1. Melon marmalade

According to the result of calculating the calorie content, the energy value of melon -rowan marmalade is 337 kcal.

The recipe for melon marmalade does not contain chemical dyes, flavors, flavor enhancers and preservatives. The finished product has a pleasant bright color and fruity aroma due to the melon and mountain ash included in the composition. The sweet taste of the finished product comes from stevioside, which is used as a sweetener in this recipe. Replacing traditional sugar with stevioside makes it possible for people with diabetes to consume this marmalade.

When calculating the recipe, threshold values for the content of melon juice in the product were set:

The minimum value is 214 kg/t. A decrease in the amount of juice leads to a deterioration in organoleptic qualities, the acquisition of a glassy and sticky surface, and a decrease in biological value.

The maximum value is 250 kg/t. Exceeding this threshold value leads to a deterioration in the consistency of the finished product, shape instability, and destruction of the product with little impact. The amount of reducing sugars in the composition of the product increases.

Among the useful chemicals in the composition of marmalade in large enough quantities are minerals such as potassium, calcium, sodium and phosphorus, as well as ascorbic acid, tocopherol and neurovitamins.

In parallel, two samples were analyzed: experimental and control. In both samples there were no coliforms, bacteria of the *Escherichia coli* group, causative agents of botulism, salmonella. The content of yeast and mold fungi in the experimental sample was 1.0×10^1 CFU/g, in the control sample of microorganisms of this group, more was found – 2.1×10^1 CFU/g, however, the results do not exceed the permissible limits.

Also, the International Commission on Microbiological Characteristics of Foods, ICMSF has set a limit for the content of the total number of microorganisms in the product, which is $>10^5$ in both samples, this parameter is also observed. Based on the results obtained, melon jelly marmalade was recognized as safe and approved for consumption [13].

The content of solids in the finished product, according to the requirements of regulatory documentation, is over 80 %, and the mass fraction of reducing substances does not exceed 20 %.

Optimal conditions and shelf life of marmalade: 1.5 months, at a temperature of +15 °C, in a place inaccessible to sunlight.

Marmalade made from the juices of gourds with the addition of rowan juice has pleasant flavor and aroma properties and high nutritional value for the diet.

Obtaining a quality product requires compliance with sanitary standards and all stages of production technology.

In the future, it is planned to carry out work to study the effect of various antioxidant compounds on the shelf life of finished marmalade [14].

4. 2. Melon Turkish Delight

According to all the requirements for the Turkish Delight product, sample No. 2 is the closest. The recipe of this sample is a reference for the manufacture of oriental sweet Turkish delight based on melon puree.

Based on the results of studies of the nutrient composition of plant raw materials (control sample) and finished oriental sweets, the following was established:

The mass fraction of fat in melon Turkish delight increased slightly – by 0.04 %.

The amount of protein in the finished product is also of little importance. The difference between melon pulp and Turkish delight is 0.35 % towards the latter.

Significant changes are observed in the content of carbohydrates. In the finished product, the amount of carbohydrates increased from 6.58 % to 17.48 %. An increase in this indicator is associated with the use of sugar and starch in the recipe, as well as with the removal of moisture during boiling.

The nutritional value of the melon product in comparison with the pulp increased by 2.4 times and amounted to 76.9 kcal.

According to the results of the analysis, a slight decrease in the content of ascorbic acid in the finished melon product was established. The finished product contains 16.2 mg/100 g, which is 0.24 mg/100 g less than melon pulp.

4. 3. Limitations and directions of research development

The developed technologies for the production of melon-based sweet products are applicable to ripe fruits with sweet pulp. When carrying out heat treatment of melon pulp puree, strict regulation of the temperature regime and the duration of boiling is mandatory. Deviations of these indicators have a sharp negative impact on the flavor and aroma properties and structure of the finished product.

5. Conclusions

As part of the study, a technology for the production of jelly marmalade and oriental sweets on a natural basis was successfully developed using local unsold melon fruits. A series of studies prove the reproducibility of this technology.

The essence of the developed technology for the production of sweet products is to address the issues of seasonality of melon fruits and the non-sale of the entire grown volume, the creation

of long-term storage products. The advantage of this development allows to reduce the sugar content in marmalade and Turkish delight, in comparison with traditional products, by 17 % and 41 %, respectively. In the production of sweet products, non-traditional raw materials are used, which allows expanding the range of sweet products and enriching the usual diet. Due to short-term heat treatment, the finished product retains a fairly high content of vitamin C, 12.37 mg/100 g in marmalade and 16.2 mg/100 g in Turkish delight, which is also a favorable factor for the introduction of the developed technology into industrial production.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

Data will be provided upon reasonable request.

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